

Role of nanotechnology in resolving the environmental issues related to air pollution

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Abstract

Environmental contamination is a serious issue today and recovery of pollutants, such as solids, heavy metals, pesticides, herbicides, fertilizers, oil spills, hazardous gases, organic compounds, industrial effluents, and wastewater, is a topic of extensive research. To rehabilitate the environment, new technologies and nano-materials are being created. Nanotechnology has an impact on a variety of disciplines, including engineering, biology, chemistry, computing, material science, military applications, and communications, in addition to its medical, ethical, mental, legal, and environmental applications. Functional groups can be added to the surface of nanomaterials to impact particular molecules for efficient recovery. Engineering nanomaterials include carbon nanotubes, nanocomposites, quantum dots, fullerenes, quantum wires, and nanofibers. Nanoporous membranes, which may contain nanotubes, are suited for mechanical filtration. The fundamental idea of molecular pollution control is to separate particular elements and molecules from a mixture of atoms and molecules. There are various ways that nanotechnology can be used to reduce air pollution.

Keywords: Air pollution, nanotechnology, nano particles, environment, applications

Introduction

In today's world, environmental contamination is a serious issue. The recovery of pollutants, such as solids, heavy metals, pesticides, herbicides, fertilizers, oil spills, hazardous gases, organic compounds, industrial effluents, and wastewater, is a topic of extensive research into new methods.¹ Because of the complexity of the compound mixture, high volatility, and low reactivity, the capture and degradation of pollutants might be challenging. To rehabilitate the environment, new technologies and nano-materials are being created. Due to the distinctive physical characteristics of its components, such as improved reactivity and efficiency from a larger surface-to-volume ratio than its volumetric equivalents, nanotechnology has attracted a lot of attention. Although nanotechnology provides clear advantages for health care and the environment, it also has the potential to create unexpected consequences that could have a negative impact on the environment, both inside the human body and in the wider ecosystem. Science must assess the environmental and health ramifications while utilizing this new technology for benefits to sustainability, health, and the environment.²

Nanotechnology has an impact on a variety of disciplines, including engineering, biology, chemistry, computing, material

science, military applications, and communications, in addition to its medical, ethical, mental, legal, and environmental applications. Nanotechnology developments might potentially be prepared to offer more sensitive detection systems for monitoring the quality of the air and water, enabling the simultaneous measurement of numerous parameters in real-time response capabilities.³ Industrial emissions are driving the development of metal oxide nano-catalysts, and as a result, titanium oxide nanoparticles' photo-catalytic characteristics are frequently used to create self-cleaning surfaces that reduce pollution. Although relatively little is known at the moment regarding the environmental impact of nanoparticles, it has been demonstrated in some circumstances that chemical composition, size, and shape can influence toxicological consequences, nanotechnology may undoubtedly offer solutions to environmental concerns. Utilizing lightweight, highly durable materials supported by carbon nanotube and metal oxide frameworks as hydrogen storage materials, nanotechnology can help with resource conservation.

Nanotechnology is described as the science of identifying and controlling materials with dimensions ranging from 1 to 100 nm that are used in new technologies due of their distinctive physical

characteristics.⁴ Thus, things smaller than 100 nm are known as nanoparticles. These particles might also have a tubular, spherical, or ad hoc shape. According to their chemical compositions, nanoparticles are split into two groups: natural and artificial nanoparticles. These two groups are then further subdivided into organic and inorganic (mineral) subgroups. Among the naturally occurring nanoparticles are fullerenes and carbon nanotubes having geogenic or pyrogenic origins. Nanostructured electrode materials for enhancing lithium-ion battery performance as well as non-porous silicon and titanium oxide in improved photovoltaic cells are other energy-related uses.

Functional groups can be added to the surface of nanomaterials to impact particular molecules for efficient recovery.⁵ Particularly when creating combinations of several materials and combining the desired properties of each component's efficiency, selectivity, and stability, the deliberate tuning of the size, morphology, porosity, and chemical composition of nanomaterials adds useful characteristics for the purification of toxicants and offers significant advantages over conventional methods of pollution control. The following techniques are employed to remove pollutants from soils, water, and air, including bacteria, pesticides, heavy metals, solvents, and oil, as well as food waste, chlorinated pesticides, and aldehydes, carboxylic acids, and NO_x.⁶ Although Richard Feynman first used the term "nanotechnology" (NT) in his writings in 1959,⁷ it wasn't until the invention of the scanning tunnelling microscope in 1981 that the term came to mean methods describing the creation and/or utilisation of nanoscale structures. Nanomaterials have non-conventional qualities and novel physicochemical traits that enable them to expand their usage in industry, environmental monitoring, health, and promotion of advanced materials and new product development. The created nanomaterials have novel physical, chemical, surface, and optical electronic properties, solve issues that cannot be resolved by conventional technologies, and contribute to the development of creative processes for producing new goods, materials, and chemicals that are highly productive and energy-efficient.

Compared to size-dependent bulk materials, particles with diameters larger than 100 nm exhibit novel characteristics. Engineering nanomaterials include carbon nanotubes, nanocomposites, quantum dots, fullerenes, quantum wires, and nanofibers.⁸ Commercial products include metals, ceramics, polymers, smart textiles, cosmetics, sunscreens, electronics, paints, and varnishes. Natural nanoparticles include erosion dust from volcanoes, wood particles from burning diesel fuel, and combustion products from diesel fuel. Nanomaterials have characteristics that make them more reactive than bulk versions of the same materials due to their high surface-to-volume ratio. For environmental recovery, nanomaterials are categorised into inorganic, carbon, and polymeric categories.

Applications of nanotechnology in environmental issues

It is reasonable to anticipate that nanochemistry will have a significant impact on technologies for wastewater treatment, air purification, and energy storage. Effective filtration processes can be achieved through mechanical or chemical means. One category of filtering methods relies on the application of membranes with appropriate pore sizes, wherein the liquid is forced through the membrane. Nanoporous membranes, which may contain nanotubes, are suited for mechanical filtration with pores as small as 10 nm. This process is known as "nanofiltration." The primary applications of nanofiltration are the elimination of ions or the division of various fluids. Utilizing magnetic separation techniques, magnetic nanoparticles provide an efficient and dependable way to remove heavy metal pollutants from wastewater.⁹ When compared to conventional precipitation and filtering procedures, using nanoscale particles increases the effectiveness of pollutant absorption and is relatively cheap. Additionally, iron nanoparticles have demonstrated promise as a detoxifying agent for removing environmental pollutants from brownfield sites.

Role of Nanotechnology in Pollution Control

Production and consumption of resources, which are currently exceedingly wasteful, lead to pollution. The majority of garbage cannot be recycled efficiently or affordably. Thus, photochemical smog, acid mine drainage, oil slicks, acid rain, and fly ash

continue to be produced by operations like the extraction, transportation, and consumption of petroleum and coal. Stephen Gillett defines the "Promethean Paradigm" in his study for the Foresight Institute as the wasteful reliance on heat for energy since burning fuel wastes a lot of its free energy during the conversion of chemical energy into heat and then to mechanical energy.¹⁰ On the other hand, biological systems effectively oxidise fuel using molecular-scale mechanisms without thermalizing the chemical energy. Reactions at the nanoscale must be under control in order to defeat the Promethean Paradigm.

The fundamental idea of molecular pollution control is to separate particular elements and molecules from a mixture of atoms and molecules. Thermal partitioning, which uses heat to create phase transitions, is the current method for separating atoms. However, both the reagent preparation and the technique itself are expensive and ineffective. The majority of the thermal energy produced by current techniques of energy extraction is squandered during combustion, which also produces undesired byproducts that need to be purified and disposed of properly. The creation of highly specialized, more effective catalysts through nanostructuring could perhaps reduce these exorbitant prices.

Unfortunately, we still haven't figured out the best technique to get the particles in usable form. The potential of nanotechnology is becoming more widely understood. Researchers from the University of Bath received the Brian Mercer Award for Innovation from the Royal Society in 2007 for their work in creating nano-porous fibres¹¹ that trap and extract carbon dioxide together with other impurities and recycle them back into the manufacturing process. Depending on their makeup and how they are spun, these fibres can recycle a variety of gases. Such technique is especially effective for applications with space constraints because to the high surface area typical of nanoscale particles.

Nanotechnology in control of air pollution

One of the biggest issues in the world is air pollution, which is the altering of the atmosphere's natural composition brought about by the introduction of chemical, physical, or biological chemicals that are

being released through anthropogenic, geogenic, or biological sources. The ecosystem (including vegetation and living things) and human health are both negatively impacted by the poor air quality, which may contribute to a number of potentially fatal diseases like cancer, respiratory, and cardiovascular conditions. Global warming, which causes numerous changes in the atmosphere, lands, and water sources all over the planet, is the main cause of outdoor air pollution.¹² Greenhouse gases are thought to be the primary cause of global warming. Carbon dioxide, methane, nitrous oxide, and fluorinated gases are the principal greenhouse gases. Growing human activity is making the GHG emission issue worse. Because most greenhouse gases have a propensity to linger in the atmosphere for hundreds of years, they tend to have enduring long-term effects on climate. Numerous control and treatment systems have been developed to stop, monitor, and reduce the threats that these gases pose to people and the environment. There are various ways that nanotechnology can be used to reduce air pollution.¹³ One way is by using nano-catalysts for gaseous processes that have more surface area. Catalysts function by accelerating chemical reactions that change hazardous vapors from automobiles and industrial facilities into safe gases. Among the catalysts currently in use is one that cleans volatile organic compounds from industrial smokestacks using nanofibers constructed of manganese oxide. There are still more approaches being developed. Nanostructured membranes with pores that are tiny enough to isolate methane or carbon dioxide from exhaust are another method. Carbon nanotubes are being studied by John Zhu of the University of Queensland in order to capture greenhouse gas emissions brought on by coal mining and energy production.¹⁴ CNT can trap gases up to 100 times faster than conventional techniques, making it possible to integrate it into massive industrial and power plants. Contrary to conventional membranes, which can only process or effectively separate large volumes of gas, this innovative technology can process and efficiently separate vast volumes of gas. The compounds that were filtered out still posed a disposal challenge because there are no net gains from taking garbage from the air just to return it to the ground. Japanese

scientists developed a method in 2006 to gather the soot removed from diesel fuel emissions and reuse it as a raw material for CNT production.¹⁵ Through laser vaporisation, the diesel soot is used to create the single-walled CNT filter, effectively turning the filtered

Conclusion

The potential and promise of nanotechnology have been continuously increasing throughout time. This new instrument in the scientific toolkit is being quickly accepted and adapted by the world. Even though there are numerous challenges to solve before this technology can be widely used, science is always improving, developing, and making strides. Many different nanomaterials are applied to environmental restoration. The optimal nanomaterial to reduce or eliminate a specific pollutant relies on the type of pollutant, the accessibility of the recovery site, the volume of material to be recovered, and the recyclable nature of the recovered material. For the elimination of various common pollutants as well as pollutants present in low quantities, traditional cleaning technologies do not provide the most economical solution. In contrast to conventional technologies, nanomaterials have the ability to remove pollutants that are present in low concentrations. Their efficiency can be improved through particle modification, and their cost can be decreased through industrial-scale production and the development of synthesis techniques that use less energy and less expensive raw materials.

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